

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of five-coordinate aluminium complexes^ψ

Nandu Bala Sharma and Anirudh Singh*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : anirudhsinghunjpr@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Complexes of the types $\text{Al(L)\{(OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{)NMe(CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH)\}}$ (where $\text{L} = \text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH=NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ (L^1) 1; $\text{L} = \text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{CH=NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ (L^2) 2) and $\text{Al\{(OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{)}_2\text{NMe}\}$ (LH) (where $\text{L} = \text{L}^1$ 3, $\text{L} = \text{L}^2$ 4) have been prepared by the reactions of $\text{Al(L)(OPr}^i\text{)}$ with $\text{MeN(CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH)}_2$ and $\text{Al\{(OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{)}_2\text{NMe}\}$ (OPrⁱ) with LH_2 in 1 : 1 molar ratio, respectively. These complexes 1, 2 and 3 react in 1 : 1 molar ratio with $\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn(OPr}^i\text{)}$ to yield heterometallic complexes 5, 6 and 7, respectively. Derivatives 1, 2 and 4 also react with Me_3SiCl in the presence of Et_3N to produce, respectively heteronuclear complexes 8, 9 and 10. All of these derivatives have been characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight measurements and spectroscopic (IR, NMR, ^1H , ^{27}Al , ^{29}Si and ^{119}Sn) studies.

Keywords : Aluminium complexes, alkoxides, heterometallic complexes.

During the last 15 years there has been enhancing interest in the heterometallic chemistry of group 13 metals¹⁻⁷ and during this period many interesting types of heterometallic alkoxides containing¹ elements of group 13 such as $\text{Mo}_2(\text{O}_2(\text{CH}_3)_2\{\text{Al(OPr}^i)_4\}_2)^8$, $\text{M}\{\text{Al(OBu}^i)_4\}_2$ ($\text{M} = \text{Mg}^{5a}$, Co , Ni , Cu^{5b}), $[(\text{HOPr}^i)_2\text{Mg}]\text{-}\{\mu\text{-OPr}^i\}_2\{\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2\}_2^9$, $[(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})_2\text{K}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2]^{10}$, $[\{\text{Pr}^i(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2\}_2\text{-}(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})\text{-}\{\mu\text{-Cl}\}]^{11}$ and $[\text{Er}\{\mu\text{-OPr}^i\}_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2]^{12}$ have been prepared and structurally characterized.

During the last few years we have developed a new pathway for the synthesis of new classes of heteronuclear alkoxide coordination systems¹³⁻¹⁷. This procedure utilizes enhanced reactivity of coordinated/hydrogen bonded hydroxy group to assemble an appropriate heterometal fragment. In view of our more encouraging achievements in this particular area, we now report in this paper the synthesis and characterization of new types of heteronuclear aluminium complexes derived from Schiff bases, methyl-diethanolamine, organosilicon and organotin moieties.

The present study assumes special significance in view of important role played by (i) heteronuclear complexes as potential precursor in Sol-Gel technology¹⁸ for ceramic thin films and coating, fibres, preforms, and speciality shapes and (ii) organo-silicon and -tin compounds¹⁹ in biochemical, agricultural and industrial fields.

Results and discussion

Equimolar reactions of $\text{Al(L)(OPr}^i\text{)\}/\text{Al\{(OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{)}_2\text{NMe}\}$ (OPrⁱ) with $\text{MeN(CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH)}_2/\text{LH}_2$ afforded an interesting type of mixed-ligand complexes in which deprotonated Schiff base moiety is bonded to aluminium in a bidentate (η^2) fashion (eqs. (1) and (2)).

Reactions of 1, 2 and 3 with $\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn(OPr}^i\text{)}$ afforded heteronuclear derivatives 5, 6 and 7, respectively (eqs. (3) and (4)).

^ψDedicated to our mentor Emeritus Professor R. C. Mehrotra (deceased on July 11, 2004) for his outstanding contributions in the fields of science and education. We always profoundly remember him

Table 1. IR (cm⁻¹) and NMR (δ, ppm) spectral data for compounds 1-10

Compd.	IR	¹ H	²⁷ Al	¹¹⁹ Sn/ ²⁹ Si
1	1640 ν(C=N), 1224 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1077 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 654 (Al-O), 515 ν(Al←N)	2.29 (3H, s, NMe), 2.56 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 2.69 (1H, s, OH), 2.96 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 2.58 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.88 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 6.46-7.41 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 8.12 (1H, s, HC=N)	13	-
2	1639 ν(C=N), 1229 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1078 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 660 (Al-O), 516 ν(Al←N)	2.29 (3H, s, NMe), 2.59 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 3.32 (1H, s, OH), 3.66 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.87 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.98 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 6.92-8.09 (6H, m, aromatic-H), 9.10 (1H, s, HC=N)	14	-
3	1640 ν(C=N), 1234 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1072 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 657 (Al-O), 517 ν(Al←N)	2.28 (3H, s, NMe), 2.58 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 2.91 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.61 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.87 (3H, t, OCH ₂ + CH ₂ OH), 6.50-7.25 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 8.13 (1H, s, HC=N)	12	-
4	1641 ν(C=N), 1234 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1075 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 656 (Al-O), 515 ν(Al←N)	2.29 (3H, s, NMe), 2.57 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 3.62 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.84 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.87 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 3.96 (1H, s, CH ₂ OH), 6.90-8.20 (6H, m, aromatic-H), 9.35 (1H, s, HC=N)	13	-
5	1640 ν(C=N), 1223 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1078 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 654 ν(Al-O), 593, 578 ν(Sn-C), 547, 531 ν(Sn-O), 517 ν(Al←N)	0.90 (9H, t, Sn(CH ₂) ₃ Me), 1.10 (6H, t, SnCH ₂ (CH ₂) ₂ Me), 1.31 (6H, m, SnCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ Me), 1.55 (6H, m, Sn(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₂ Me), 2.33 (3H, s, NMe), 2.57 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 2.69 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.57 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.81 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 6.50-7.21 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 8.13 (1H, s, HC=N)	13	103
6	1641 ν(C=N), 1229 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1076 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 660 ν(Al-O), 594, 578 ν(Sn-C), 546, 531 ν(Sn-O), 516 ν(Al←N)	0.92 (9H, t, Sn(CH ₂) ₃ Me), 1.14 (6H, t, SnCH ₂ (CH ₂) ₂ Me), 1.32 (6H, m, SnCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ Me), 1.59 (6H, m, Sn(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₂ Me), 2.32 (3H, s, NMe), 2.59 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 3.60 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.74 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.95 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 6.88-8.02 (6H, m, aromatic-H), 9.08 (1H, s, HC=N)	14	103
7	1640 ν(C=N), 1234 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1072 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 656 ν(Al-O), 594, 578 ν(Sn-C), 545, 531, ν(Sn-O), 516 ν(Al←N)	0.89 (9H, m, Sn(CH ₂) ₃ Me), 1.15 (6H, t, SnCH ₂ (CH ₂) ₂ Me), 1.32 (6H, m, SnCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ Me), 1.54 (6H, m, Sn(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₂ Me), 2.35 (3H, s, NMe), 2.56 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 2.60 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.61 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.80 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 6.50-7.22 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 8.15 (1H, s, HC=N)	13	94
8	1640 ν(C=N), 1235 ν(Si-Me) deformation, 1234 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1062 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 904 ν(Si-O), 830 ρ _r (Si-Me), 750 ν(Si-C), 655 ν(Al-O), 672 ν(Si-C), 625 ν(Si-O), 518 ν(Al←N)	0.11 (9H, s, SiMe ₃), 2.31 (3H, s, NMe), 2.58 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 2.71 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.55 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.85 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 6.58-7.19 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 8.18 (1H, s, HC=N)	13	24
9	1640 ν(C=N), 1231 ν(Si-Me) deformation, 1234 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1062 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 904 ν(Si-O), 828 ρ _r (Si-Me), 753 ν(Si-C), 651 ν(Al-O), 628 ν(Si-O), 516 ν(Al←N)	0.26 (9H, s, SiMe ₃), 2.11 (3H, s, NMe), 2.59 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 3.62 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.83 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.94 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 7.18-8.50 (6H, m, aromatic-H), 9.30 (1H, s, HC=N)	14	21
10	1640 ν(C=N), 1236 ν(Si-Me) deformation, 1234 ν(C-O) phenolic, 1067 ν(C-O) alcoholic, 905 ν(Si-O), 831 ρ _r (Si-Me), 754 ν(Si-C), 672 ν(Si-C), 650 ν(Al-O), 626 ν(Si-O), 515 ν(Al←N)	0.12 (9H, s, SiMe ₃), 2.31 (3H, s, NMe), 2.59 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 3.54 (4H, t, OCH ₂), 3.61 (2H, t, NCH ₂ (L)), 3.75 (2H, t, OCH ₂ (L)), 6.85-8.20 (6H, m, aromatic-H), 9.31 (1H, s, HC=N)	14	24

Interactions of 1, 2 and 4 with Me₃SiCl in the presence of Et₃N (eqs. (5) and (6)) yielded derivatives 8-10.

All of these derivatives 1-10 are yellow solids (Table 2), soluble in typical organic solvents and exhibit (cryoscopically) monomeric behaviour in benzene solution.

Spectral studies :

IR spectra :

Derivatives 1-10 exhibit structurally important absorption bands (Table 1) at 1640 ± 2 cm⁻¹ ν(C=N), 1230 ± 4 cm⁻¹ ν(C-O) phenolic, 1070 ± 8 cm⁻¹ ν(C-O) alcoholic. The observed lowering in ν(C=N) may be interpreted in terms of intramolecular coordination^{17,20} of azomethine nitrogen to aluminium. Other important absorption bands^{16a,17,21-23} are observed at 1237 ± 8 cm⁻¹ ν(Si-Me) deformation, 909 ± 6 cm⁻¹ ν(Si-O), 830 ± 2 cm⁻¹ ρ_r(Si-Me), 750 ± 4 cm⁻¹ ν(Si-C), 655 ± 5 cm⁻¹ ν(Al-O), 593 ± 1, 577 ± 1 cm⁻¹ ν(Sn-C), 546 ± 1, 531 cm⁻¹ ν(Sn-O) and 516 ± 2 cm⁻¹ ν(Al←N).

¹H NMR spectra :

As expected derivatives 1-10 showed signals characteristics of *N*-methyl-diethanolamine^{15c,20} moiety at δ 2.22 ± 0.12 (NMe), 2.63 ± 0.05 (NCH₂), 3.62 ± 0.03 (OCH₂) and

Table 2. Preparative and analytical details for aluminium derivatives based on Schiff bases and *N*-methyldiethanolamine

Reactants (g, mmol)	Liberated Pr ⁺ OH or precipitated Et ₃ N HCl	Product ^{a,b} Empirical formula, colour and state ^c yield (g)	Analysis (%) Found (Calcd)					
			Al	Sn	C	H	N	
Al(L ¹)(OPr ^t) (1 59, 6 38)	MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) (0 76, 6 37)	0 38 (0 38)	Al(L ¹ {MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O)(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH)}) 1 C ₁₄ H ₂₁ AlN ₂ O ₄ (1 49)	8 74 (8 75)	–	54 41 (54 48)	6 81 (6 86)	9 01 (9 08)
Al(L ²)(OPr ^t) (1 70, 5 67)	MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) (0 67, 5 62)	0 34 (0 34)	Al(L ² {MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O)(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH)}) 2 C ₁₈ H ₂₃ AlN ₂ O ₄ (1 46)	7 12 (7 53)	–	60 21 (60 26)	6 40 (6 46)	7 78 (7 81)
Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(OPr ^t) (0 73, 3 59)	H ₂ L ¹ (0 59, 3 57)	0 21 (0 21)	Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(L ¹ H) 3 C ₁₄ H ₂₁ AlN ₂ O ₄ (0 83)	8 65 (8 75)	–	54 40 (54 48)	6 84 (6 86)	9 00 (9 08)
Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(OPr ^t) (1 68 5 61)	H ₂ L ² (0 67, 5 62)	0 33 (0 34)	Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(L ² H) 4 C ₁₈ H ₂₃ AlN ₂ O ₄ (2 22)	7 14 (7 53)	–	60 20 (60 26)	6 40 (6 46)	7 78 (7 81)
Al(L ¹){(CH ₂ CH ₂ O)NMe- (CH ₂ CH ₂ OH)} (0 71 2 30)	Bu ₃ Sn(OPr ^t) (0 80, 2 29)	0 14 (0 14)	Al(L ¹){MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ } SnBu ₃ 5 C ₂₆ H ₄₇ AlN ₂ O ₄ Sn (1 35)	4 30 (4 51)	19 75 (19 86)	52 20 (52 22)	8 10 (8 09)	4 60 (4 68)
Al(L ²){(CH ₂ CH ₂ O)NMe(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH)} (0 98, 2 73)	Bu ₃ Sn(OPr ^t) (0 95, 2 72)	0 16 (0 16)	Al(L ²){MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ } SnBu ₃ 6 C ₃₀ H ₄₉ AlN ₂ O ₄ Sn (1 73)	4 14 (4 17)	18 09 (18 33)	55 58 (55 60)	7 71 (7 78)	4 30 (4 32)
Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(L ¹ H) (0 93, 3 01)	Bu ₃ Sn(OPr ^t) (1 05, 3 00)	0 17 (0 18)	Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(L ¹) SnBu ₃ 7 C ₂₆ H ₄₇ AlN ₂ O ₄ Sn (1 70)	4 42 (4 51)	19 19 (19 86)	52 20 (52 22)	8 04 (8 09)	4 66 (4 68)
Al(L ¹){(CH ₂ CH ₂ O)NMe- (CH ₂ CH ₂ OH)} (1 09 3 53)	Me ₃ SiCl Et ₃ N (0 38, 3 50) (0 37, 3 65)	0 47 (0 48)	Al(L ¹){MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ } SiMe ₃ 8 C ₁₇ H ₂₉ AlN ₂ O ₄ Si (1 33)	7 01 (7 09)	7 30 (7 37)	53 52 (53 60)	7 90 (7 94)	7 34 (7 35)
Al(L ²){(CH ₂ CH ₂ O)NMe- (CH ₂ CH ₂ OH)} (1 33, 3 71)	Me ₃ SiCl Et ₃ N (0 40, 3 68) (0 37, 3 65)	0 50 (0 51)	Al(L ²){MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ } SiMe ₃ 9 C ₂₁ H ₃₁ AlN ₂ O ₄ Si (1 20)	6 20 (6 27)	6 40 (6 52)	58 49 (58 52)	7 42 (7 49)	6 47 (6 50)
Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(L ² H) (1 58, 4 40)	Me ₃ SiCl Et ₃ N (0 48, 4 41) (0 45, 4 44)	0 59 (0 61)	Al{MeN(CH ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ }(L ²) SiMe ₃ 10 C ₂₁ H ₃₁ AlN ₂ O ₄ Si (1 36)	6 24 (6 27)	6 41 (6 52)	58 51 (58 52)	7 44 (7 49)	6 42 (6 50)

^aAbbreviations L¹ = OC₆H₄CH=NCH₂CH₂O. L² = OC₁₀H₆CH=NCH₂CH₂O

^bAll are monomeric, ^cAll are yellow solids

for the Schiff base group^{17b,17c} at δ 3.80 \pm 0.06 (NCH₂), 3.96 \pm 0.02 (OCH₂), 6.50–8.21 (aromatic-*H*) and 8.12–9.35 (HC=N). Derivatives 1, 2 and 3, 4 show signals for OH group in the δ 3.30–3.32 and 3.87–3.96 ppm regions, respectively. Heterometallic derivatives 5, 6 and 7 exhibit signals^{17,24} (Table 1) at δ 0.89–0.92 (Me(CH₂)₃Sn), 1.10–1.19 (MeCH₂(CH₂)₂Sn), 1.31–1.32 (MeCH₂CH₂CH₂Sn) and 1.55–1.59 (Me(CH₂)₂CH₂Sn). Heteronuclear derivatives 8–10 show singlets due to Me₃Si group in the δ 0.11–0.39 ppm region.

²⁷Al NMR spectra :

Derivatives 1–10 exhibit ²⁷Al NMR signals (Table 1) in the δ 12–14 ppm region, consistent with pentacoordinate²⁵ aluminium compounds (Fig. 1).

¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

Derivatives 5, 6 and 7 showed ¹¹⁹Sn NMR signals (Table 1) in the δ 91–105 ppm region, in agreement with tetracoordinate²⁶ tributyltin(IV) compounds (Fig. 1).

²⁹Si NMR spectra :

The observed ²⁹Si NMR signals for 8, 9 and 10 in the δ 21–24 ppm region supports the structural formulation shown in Fig. 1, with silicon in four-coordinate environment²³.

Fig. 1. Plausible structure of heteronuclear derivatives 5–10

Experimental

All synthesis and manipulations were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions. Solvents were made anhydrous by standard²⁷ methods and freshly distilled prior to use. Isopropoxides of aluminium²⁸ and tributyltin⁷ were prepared by the literature methods. Precursor derivatives²⁹

Al(L)(OPr'), Al{MeN(CH₂CH₂O)₂}(OPr') and Schiff bases³⁰ were prepared by the methods reported in the literature Aluminium was determined as oxinate³¹. Tin and silicon were determined as their oxides³¹. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method³¹. Isopropyl alcohol in the azeotrope was determined oxidimetrically³². Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in benzene solution. ¹H (300.40 MHz), ²⁷Al (78.19 MHz), ²⁹Si (59.60 MHz) and ¹¹⁹Sn (119.95 MHz) were recorded in CDCl₃ on JEOL FT AL 300 spectrometer. IR spectra (4000-400 cm⁻¹) were recorded as Nujol mulls a Nicolet Magna 550 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Al(OC₆H₄CH=NCH₂CH₂O){MeN(CH₂CH₂O)(CH₂CH₂OH)} 1 :

The yellow solution in benzene (~45 ml) containing Al(OC₆H₄CH=NCH₂CH₂O)(OPr') (1.59 g, 6.38 mmol) and MeN(CH₂CH₂OH)₂ (0.76 g, 6.37 mmol) was refluxed for ~4 h. The liberated isopropyl alcohol (0.38 g) was fractionated out during the above mentioned time and determined. After completion of the reaction, which was evident by the absence of an oxidizable species in the azeotrope collected thereafter. The volatile components from solution were removed under reduced pressure to yield a yellow solid (1.95 g). Recrystallization from 2 : 1 mixture of dichloromethane and *n*-hexane at -20 °C gave the title compound as a yellow solid (1.49 g, 76%).

Derivatives 2-4 were also prepared in a manner similar to that was employed for 1. Preparative and analytical details are listed in Table 2.

Preparation of Al(OC₆H₄CH=NCH₂CH₂O){MeN(CH₂CH₂O)₂}SnBu₃ 5 :

To a benzene solution (~40 ml) of Al(OC₆H₄CH=NCH₂CH₂O){MeN(CH₂CH₂O)(CH₂CH₂OH)} (0.71 g, 2.30 mmol), was added Bu₃Sn(OPr') (0.80 g, 2.29 mmol) and the resulting yellow solution was refluxed under a fractionating column with continuous removal of the liberated isopropyl alcohol, which was collected and determined (0.14 g). When the distillate showed negligible presence of isopropyl alcohol, the refluxing was stopped and reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to obtain yellow semisolid (1.37 g), which was dissolved in 2 : 1 mixture of dichloromethane and *n*-hexane and kept at -20 °C for several days but no crystallisation had occurred. The product was, therefore, isolated as a yellow solid after removal of the solvent. Yield 1.35 (98%).

Derivatives 6 and 7 were also prepared by the procedure similar to that was used for 5. Preparative and analytical details are listed in Table 2.

Al(OC₆H₄CH=NCH₂CH₂O){MeN(CH₂CH₂O)₂}SiMe₃ 8

To a solution of Me₃SiCl (0.38 g, 3.50 mmol) and Et₃N (0.36 g, 3.65 mmol) in benzene (~10 ml) was added a solution of Al(OC₆H₄CH=NCH₂CH₂O){MeN(CH₂CH₂O)(CH₂CH₂OH)} (1.09 g, 3.53 mmol) dissolved in benzene (~15 ml). The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature (~32 °C) for ~4 h. The precipitated Et₃N.HCl (0.47 g) was removed by filtration. Volatile components from the solution were removed under reduced pressure to yield a yellow semisolid. The product was dissolved in 2 : 1 mixture of dichloromethane and *n*-hexane and kept at -20 °C for several days but no crystallization took place. The solvent was then removed to obtain yellow solid (1.33 g, 99%).

Adopting a similar procedure derivatives 9 and 10 were also prepared. Preparative and analytical details are listed in Table 2.

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